

Deep-tech driven inclusive and socially-aware circular material joining & welding for a safe future

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D1.1 Project Management Plan

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1. Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
AB	Advisory Board
DG	Dissemination Group
EC	European Commission
GA	General Assembly
SC	Strategic Committee
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Officer
QCP	Quality Control Panel
QAM	Quality Assurance Manager
StC	Steering Committee
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Terminology	
Conformity	The fulfilment of a specified requirement by a quality characteristic of an item or service, the assessment of which does not depend essentially on time.
Quality system	The organizational structure, responsibilities, activities, resources and events that together provide organized procedures and methods of implementation to ensure the capability of the Partner / Consortium to meet quality requirements.
Quality	The totality of features and characteristics of a prototype or service that bear on its ability to satisfy a given need.

2. Executive Summary

This document presents the «**Project Management Plan**» of the **WELDIFY** project that complements the information provided in the «**Grant Agreement**» and «**Description of Action**», integrating more detailed procedures.

The main objective of «**Deliverable 1.1**» is to establish and maintain a quality control program to be followed by project partners throughout the course of the project. The manual sets directions, practices and strategies for ensuring high quality performance of the project deliverables and undertakings.

The Management Plan specifies the activities that need to be implemented, including their sequence, in order to ensure that the project and its deliverables fully conform to the objectives that have been set. The Plan is to be used by:

- The consortium partners that will be responsible for monitoring the project activities.
- The consortium partners that will be responsible for preparing and amending the project's deliverables.
- The consortium partners that will be responsible for reviewing and approving specific activities to be undertaken for completing the respective project's deliverables.

The main components of the «**Project Management Plan**» can be summarized to the following:

- Project Management structure
- Quality plan procedure
- Quality Evaluation
- Documentation control procedures (templates, layout, coding, etc.)
- Strategies for the project internal communication
- Risk mitigation measures

3. Introduction

3.1. Purpose of the document

The main objective of this document is to make the cooperation among WELDIFY partners easier and more efficient, giving a complete guideline with all information, rules and procedures so that the scientific outcomes comply with the WELDIFY project's work plan and contractual obligations and results fulfil the technical requirements set by the WELDIFY Consortium for effective progress toward the achievement of the project goals.

The WELDIFY Project Management Plan (**PMP**) is based on several principles that are important in inter-organizational collaboration:

1. An effective Project Management relies on collaboration and cooperation among partners. The WELDIFY partners are collaborating to achieve a common objective, share experience and know-how, and develop results with complementary skills;
2. Work must be organised and planned in a result-driven way. While the internal organisation of each partner's work depends on him/her (as long as he meets his/her commitments), the interactions between partners working at distance must be based on the flow of results. Common planning must hence be a reference for everybody and must always be up-to-date;
3. The collaboration between partners is based on consensus and joint decision-making, involving different levels of decision-makers in different domains (strategic, technical, financial, and administrative). The decisions will be achieved by "rough consensus and running code (or experiments)", using formal procedures such as voting only when essential. The rules for such decision-making need to be clear;
4. The effectiveness of meetings between partners is absolutely critical to the progress of work. An inconclusive meeting can cause serious delays, risks and costs;
5. Effective collaboration requires central coordination and logistics support. The coordination mechanisms, communication flow inside and outside the project are supported by the WELDIFY management structure;
6. Resource control will be achieved by evaluating «Earned Value» through the assessment of intermediate level of completion of deliverables.

This document has been prepared to describe the implementation of the above principles.

3.2. Procedure description

Quality planning is an integral part of management planning. As a prerequisite to its preparation, the Quality Control Panel (2.2.5) has reviewed all requirements in order to determine the necessary activities that need to be planned.

It has been prepared early in the project in order to demonstrate and provide the Consortium with the assurance that:

- contract requirements and conditions have been reviewed,
- effective quality planning has taken place, and
- the quality system is appropriate.

To ensure relevance of the quality plan, the Quality Control Panel should conduct quality reviews, throughout the duration of the contract, and when contractual changes occur. The Quality Control Panel shall ensure that the quality plan is available to all partners concerned and that its requirements are met.

4. Management Plan

4.1. Management Structure and procedures

WELDIFY project encompasses **13 partners** and **7 independent** work packages. The overall management structure is illustrated in Figure 1 and it has been designed to achieve the following goals:

1. Reasonable distribution of activities and responsibilities among all 13 partners by also considering their respective competences;
2. Efficient vertical and horizontal information flow, especially between work packages;
3. Robust structures and procedures for responsive and cost-effective project management;
4. Optimal assignment of experienced personnel to the scientific, technical and managerial tasks;
5. Identified potential risks and associated contingency plans.

The **Project Coordinator** undertakes the detailed project planning and delivery responsibility and interfaces with the European Commission for compliance with all requirements. The **Strategic Committee** makes executive decisions on strategic issues and has a major impact on the success of the partnership. For the purpose of the management and the successful

execution decisions on strategic issues and has a major impact on the success of the partnership. For the purpose of the management and the successful execution of all tasks, the **Work Package Leaders** and the **Task Leaders** fulfil these roles. The requirements of tasks and deliverables are specific but relate to the maturity reached by the project in relation to the Quality Control Panel's expectations for the work under review. The Quality Control Panel is responsible for reviewing the project's results and giving the clearance to proceed to the next step. Regarding the updates of the dissemination plan, the Dissemination Group will identify new opportunities and evaluate outcomes and the quality of relevant activities. Finally, the **Advisory Board** will support the implementation of the WELDIFY project providing feedback at key project milestones

4.2. Project Management

4.2.1. Project Coordinator (PC)

The Hellenic Institute of Transport of the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is the **Project Coordinator (PC)** for both administrative and technical aspects. The PC is the liaison between the project and the **European Commission (EC)** which is represented by the **Project Officer (PO)**. The PC is responsible for the quality of work that is being held in the project having the utmost administrative, managerial and scientific responsibility for the **WELDIFY** project. The coordinating body is responsible also to formulate and submit all necessary reports to the EC, which monitors the project's progress.

The main responsibilities of the PC are:

- overall management of the project and, in particular, of administrative duties, scientific and quality assurance, budget monitoring, risk and contingency planning and proper documentation of these issues in conjunction with financial needs;
- reporting of project's findings and consolidation of partner contribution into a single final report;
- interfacing with the European Commission for all necessary issues under the umbrella of the WELDIFY project (contractual issues, project content, amendments, reporting, communication, dissemination and take-up planning);
- representation to the research community.

4.2.2. Strategic Committee (SC)

The **Strategic Committee (SC)** is the superior governing body of WELDIFY. It represents every partner in the Consortium and is empowered to review compliance of members with the Consortium Agreement and with the stated goals of the project. It is composed of one delegate per partner organization and shall meet physically at least once a year and virtually as needed. The SC takes final decisions on policy and contractual issues and conflicts as requested by the Coordinator. Each delegate has one vote; decisions are made by consensus whenever possible. Only in cases where consensus is not possible, decisions are made by majority voting. The majority rule is detailed in the Consortium Agreement.

The main responsibilities of the **SC** consist of:

- reviewing general project progress with regard to its goals;
- deciding on actions in case of major deviations from the plan;
- discussing and making decisions on changes in the Consortium structure;
- deciding on re-allocation of the budget;
- approving planned contract amendments to the Grant Agreement;
- approving changes to Consortium Agreement;
- deciding on collaborations, if large strategic impacts are expected by the Coordinator.
- resolving conflicts that cannot be solved at lower management levels.

4.2.3. Steering Committee (StC)

The «**Steering Committee**» consists of the Coordinator (chair) and all WP leaders. In addition, the «**StC**» may include additional members, to ensure that all major project perspectives will be covered. The StC composition will be ratified by the **SC**. The **StC** will make executive decisions on strategic issues and will have a major impact on the overall outcomes and success of the partnership. Major decisions regarding the project's overall technological direction will be made here in close collaboration with an external advisory board (**EQAB-2.2.10**). The «StC» will make recommendations for amendments of the EC Grant Agreement for GA ratification. Overall, the StC is subject to the decisions made by the SC.

4.2.4. Work Package leaders and task leaders (WPL and TL)

The WP leader (WPL) is responsible for the management and execution of all tasks in the affiliated work package and for resolving any critical issues at WP level. The WPL is responsible for submitting the deliverables produced by its WP to the SC in time. The WPL also reports to the

Project Coordinator about the status on a regular basis or when asked for. The WPL should monitor the progress of the work package (in terms of timing of submissions or quality control, scientific context and correspondence to the agreed level of quality) and coordinate the tasks at WP level. In case of any identified delays that may have impact to WP deliverables or the deliverables' submission of other WPs the WPL has to inform the PC. Task leader (TL) is responsible for the work to be accomplished at task level. Tasks are components of each work package that include a specific and consistent set of activities, being part of the whole WP. The task leader is responsible for the management and execution of associated task and report to the WPL.

Work Package No	Work Package Name	Leader
WP1	Project management and coordination	CERTH
WP2	Circular material for welding (CMW) training content development	CERTH
WP3	Micro credential certification framework	HELIX
WP4	WELDIFY CMW Platform	YET
WP5	Work-based learning pilots	CTA
WP6	Monitoring and evaluation	IMPACT
WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation & Impact	EITM

Table 1 Description of WPs

4.2.5. Quality Control Panel

The Quality Control Panel (QCP) will be established for the discussion and review of project's findings and results throughout the duration of the project and will serve as the external quality control panel of the work that is elaborated within the «WELDIFY» project. QCP is established to guarantee effective research results, as well as to enhance their accessibility to key stakeholders and to provide a channel for discussion of the implications of adopting specific policies. The committee will consist of the Project Coordinator (CERTH) and the members of the

Steering Committee (one representative from each partner organization) to supervise the processes. The members were already decided during the kick-off meeting. Additionally, the quality assurance processes will be supported by a Quality Assurance Manager (QAM), and an External Quality Assurance Board (EQAB) will be involved in overseeing the project's monitoring and evaluation, ensuring alignment with its goals and anticipated outcomes.

To support better implementation, pairing among partners (administrative mentorship) will be done to help less experienced consortium members handle the implementation flow & administration flow of the project: CERTH-CTA; EWF-HELIX; IIW-ISIM; HU-IMPACTCI-SUDOTIM; REDASP- CSC.

The project will have a strict quality control system for all its outputs and QA will be done firstly through internal peer-review by the QCP (coordinated by the QAM). Secondly, an external advisory board (EQAB) and External Evaluator will perform quality checks at three levels for each output (prototype/concept, interim draft and final draft). The WELDIFY project deliverables will be subject to quality review by the QCP. The responsible author(s) for each deliverable will then be assigned to recompile, adjust, clarify, modify etc. of what has been suggested to be reconsidered. A detailed plan for the internal quality review will foresee the use of a template that will serve as the common backbone for quality assurance reviewers.

The main areas that should be under quality review are:

- The technical approach pursued within the deliverable;
- The level or relation to the objectives of the deliverable as described in the relevant description of work to be done
- Quality of the results produced within the deliverable in accordance to those expected
- Format, language, presentation and grammar / syntax.

Each deliverable will be accompanied (introduced) by an executive summary explaining in short, the project phase (understanding, toolkit, implementation, evaluation, guidance), the specific problem addressed in this phase and analyzed in the deliverable, the solution developed for this problem, the value-added of the solution (in comparison with what has been achieved until then), and the exploitation potential of outcomes. In order to strengthen and justify the partner contribution to project deliverables, a contribution form will be distributed to involved partners that should reflect the contribution from each partner (what has been done and how many person months were spent for this). Each partner who will provide input to each deliverable should fill in and send this template to WP leader and Project Coordinator. This will enhance visibility of the work done and provide evidence of the resources allocated.

4.2.6. Dissemination Group (DG)

The Dissemination Group (DG) consists of the Coordinator, QAM, StC and the leader of the Dissemination WP (WP7). The Project Dissemination Leader is «EITM». The dissemination group will meet regularly in teleconferences to review and plan the dissemination activities. The role of the DG is to review the updates of the dissemination plan, to identify new dissemination opportunities, and to evaluate the outcomes and the quality of the dissemination activities.

4.2.7. Quality assurance & evaluation

A quality plan will be developed to define specific quality performance indicators in each output of the project based on: (i) process and project management, (ii) partnership; (iii) results. The quality plan will: define all the evaluation tools that will be used; describe clear evaluation criteria; create a shared understanding of the purposes, use, and users of the evaluation results; foster project's transparency to stakeholders and decision makers; facilitate evaluation capacity building among partners and stakeholders and also best evaluation practices.

4.2.8. Evaluation procedure

The evaluation procedure will be based on: Analysis of project outputs and long-term outcomes (including the identification of improvements); Observations of interactions during implementation of all project activities; Surveys of personnel from partner organisations; Evaluation forms from participants in dissemination events and «WELDIFY» blended pilots; Assessment of the skill-gap mitigation of target groups (beginning vs end of the project) via competence grids; External peer review based on an External Quality Assurance Board (EQAB); External evaluation with midterm and final reports by an appointed External Evaluator (see WP6). A sample of the quality assurance and evaluation indicators can be found below:

Table 2 – Quality/ Evaluation indicators during the project implementation timeline				
Indicator	Base value	Target value	Measurement unit	Measurement method
CMW modules developed and integrated into university curricula (quant)	0	5	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
CMW modules developed and	0	5	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed

integrated into VET curricula (quant)				
Number of project partners registered as DTTI pledgers	2	14	Number of registered partners	DTTI Pledge confirmation
CMW modules developed and integrated into the DTTI Pledge	0	5	Number of modules	Approval from the DTTI Team
Number of train-the-trainers modules (quant)	0	5	Number of modules	Complete learning pack developed
Number of trained learners on CMW (quant)	0	5000	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of trained trainers in CMW (quant)	0	250	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of learners from social groups at risk involved in the project (quant) - particularly disabilities (visible and invisible)	0	500	# of certifications	Record/log keeping
Number of learners involved in blended work-based learning secondments (quant)	0	100	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping
Number of companies engaged in the WELDIFY platform (quant)	0	100	Number of registrations	Record/log keeping

Number of universities and VET centres that will uptake the WELDIFY platform (quant)	0	50	Number of companies	Record/log keeping
Number of modernised university and VET related CMW curricula (quant)	0	25	Number of institutions	Record/log keeping
Learner satisfaction with regards to the WELDIFY online platform (quant + qual) - 35% increase from day 1 to end of training	0	> 85% satisfaction with	1-5 scale index	Perceptions survey with regards to learner satisfaction
Make CMW workforce more productive (quant)	Index-based	20% increase	Productivity metrics	Checking company reports
Learner digital competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	35% increase	1-5 point scale for DigComp	Self-assessed DigComp survey (pre and post training)
Learner green competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	30% increase	1-5 point scale for GreenComp	Self-assessed GreenComp survey (pre and post training)
Learner entrepreneurship competence increase (sample of 1000 learners) (quant)	after pre-assessment	35% increase	1-5 point scale for EntreComp	Self-assessed EntreComp survey (pre and post training)

Trainer competence increase with regards to online education delivery (sample of 250 trainers) (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% increase	1-5 point scale for DigCompEdu	Self-assessed DigCompEdu survey (pre and post training)
Number of dropouts from university/VET (quant)	after pre-assessment	25% decrease	Number of learners	Comparing dropouts in year 1 and in year 3 learners database
Amount of funding obtained to sustain WELDIFY activities (quant)	0	500 000	EUR	Combined budget from new projects required to sustain WELDIFY' efforts
# of policy makers interested to use WELDIFY platform for promoting regional safety, sustainability and industrial resilience (quant)	0	20	Number of policy makers	Record/log keeping
Number of companies outside of the consortium interested to use WELDIFY platform for upskilling their employees (quant)	0	30	Number of companies	Record/log keeping
Make online education more inclusive (quant + qual)	after pre-assessment	45% increase	Subjective/personal reflections	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)
Degree of learners feeling empowered to be in charge of their own learning path (quant + qual)	TBD after pre-assessment	30% increase	Subjective/personal reflections on key indicators	Pre and post assessment (before and after the trainings)

Increase employability of	Statistical average	15-30% increase in 6-12 months	Percentage	Comparing yearly statistics
Overall satisfaction level of the involved project team (quant + qual)	0	>85%	Subjective reflections	Post assessment at the project completion
Social media engagements / impressions (quant)	0	100000	# of impressions	Social media metrics
Website visitors (quant)	0	5000	# of visitors	Google analytics
Implementation conformance (quant)	0	<10% change	Percentage	Measuring timeline changes

Table 2 Quality/ Evaluation indicators during the project implementation timeline

4.2.9. Monitoring and evaluation process

WELDIFYs' quality processes will be led by IMPACTsci, specifically by Andreia Morgado as a Quality Assurance Manager (QAM), will spearhead the quality assurance processes for WELDIFY, leveraging her extensive experience with Erasmus+ projects. She will chair a quality control committee composed of members from each partner organization. The Quality Assurance Manager (from IMPACTsci), Project Coordinator (from CERTH), the Steering Group (SG), and the EQAB will oversee the project's monitoring and evaluation, aiming for its goals and anticipated outcomes. Quality control and evaluation points:

Financial management: Biannual formal financial reports and quarterly informal updates

Project Implementation Checks: Monthly reviews during calls to ensure adherence to the project timeline.

Deliverables and Results Review: A dual-stage review process, starting with an internal peer review one month before deadlines, followed by an external peer review (to the external advisory board) one month prior, covering all work package outputs. This applies to both formal

results as well as to progress results (i.e. pilot methodologies, dissemination materials, etc all broken down per task defined in each WP).

Staff Engagement Surveys: Quarterly surveys to monitor staff participation levels.

Meeting Evaluations: Immediate assessments post-meeting via «EWF» designed online surveys, evaluating preparations, in-meeting activities, and outcomes (online questionnaire).

Dissemination Event Feedback: Post-event evaluations by «EITM» to assess the organization, facilitation, and attendee experience through evaluation questionnaires administered immediately after each event.

Platform Pilot Assessments: Pre- and post-execution evaluations of pilots using EITM questionnaires to assess various aspects such as organisation, user experience, and competency levels. Interim Quality Reports: Biannual reports summarising findings from all evaluations.

External Evaluation: Independent evaluations by appointed evaluator at mid-term and project conclusion. These activities will be contextualised within a SWOT analysis, offering a detailed quantitative and qualitative examination of the project's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.

4.2.10. External quality assurance board (EQAB)

An advisory board of four (4) external, independent experts, representatives of top-rated projects and influencers in the field will be created and established, covering the identified WELDIFY themes, so as to closely monitor and directly provide consultation to the training and capacity-building development activities.

4.2.11. Consortium as a whole

The WELDIFY project Consortium includes 13 partners from 10 Countries (presented in the table below).

No	Consortium	Short Name	Country	Profile
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL	Research Centre
2	HOGSKOLAN I HALMSTAD	HU	SE	University
3	YET ASTIKI MI KERGOSKOPIKI ETAIREIA	YET	EL	Training Centre

4	HELIXCONNECT EUROPE SRL	HELIXCONNECT	RO	Research Centre
5	INSTITUTUL NATIONAL DE CERCETARE DEZVOLTARE IN SUDURA SI INCERCARI DE MATERIALE - ISIM TIMISOARA	ISIM	RO	Public certified VET provider
6	EIT MANUFACTURING EAST GMBH	EITM	AT	European level Institute
7	INTERNATIONAL INSTITUTE OF WELDING IIW	IIW	IT	International level Institute
8	EUROPEAN FEDERATION FOR WELDING JOINING AND CUTTING	EFW	BE	International level Industrial Association
9	FUNDACION CORPORACION TECNOLOGICA DE ANDALUCIA	CTA	ES	Private Foundation
10	REGIONALNA AGENCIJA ZA EKONOMSKI RAZVOJ SUMADIJE I POMORAVLJA	REDASP	RS	Regional Economic Development Agency
11	C.S CENTER FOR SUSTAINABILITY LIMITED	CSC	CY	Training Centre
12	IMPACTSCI, UNIPessoal LDA	IMPACTSCI	PT	Start – up
13	SUDOTIM AS SRL	SUDOTIM	RO	Manufacturing SME

Table 3 – WELDIFY Partners

WELDIFY has a very well-defined and professional consortium management and coordination process as shown in the respective section of the application, however, what is more important, WELDIFY puts a strong emphasis on team spirit especially since part of the activities will be done online, with the risk of disengagement. To this end, there are several mitigating factors that will ensure a strong team spirit and an excellent cooperation: Firstly, the partners have past collaboration experience: i.e. HELIX and YET collaborated in more than 10 Erasmus+ projects. CERTH, YET and ISIM collaborated in 1 such projects as well as in regional events that aimed at spurring competence building, HELIX and ISIM staff collaborated in past industrial PM program delivery (university level). ISIM, IIW (VET providers) and EFW are constant partners in intensive R&D and Erasmus + projects in the field of welding, manufacturing and industrial engineering, ISIM has long lasting collaboration with SUDOTIM while HELIX has been collaborating for 2 years with IMPACTSCI, REDASP, CTA, CSC on different proposals, transnational initiatives and capacity

building actions, HELIX and HU are partners in 1 project; EITM, HELIX and ISIM have been previously involved in regional projects aimed at developing VET education programs, HELIX and EITM have an intensive collaboration as part of the EIT-HEI initiative and efforts to transform universities. Secondly, the project will promote a dual team-spirit: both during task implementation by instituting a collegial work environment and actively promoting a helpful attitude (coordinator is in charge and WP leaders will implement such an approach); as well as socially: WELDIFY will ensure that team building and social activities are included during the in-person events as well as that informal social interaction (i.e. LinkedIn groups, hybrid social cafes before/after formal meetings) will be enabled in order to facilitate a quicker and more stable team bonding. Thirdly, to devise a proper team building strategy, the partners will agree on a standardised set of methods during the kick off meeting that will be constantly updated based on the needs and on the measured engagement level of the team.

4.2.12. Consortium management and decision-making

WELDIFY leverages the best practices gained from its project partners across over 300 successfully completed funded projects, employing a structured management framework divided into four key levels for optimal control and action: **Micro-level Strategy:** Concentrates on specific task-level activities, fostering innovations and conceptual developments through detailed work packages (WPs). **Meso-level Strategy:** Targets broader project strategies and policies, overseen by the Strategic Committee (SC). **Meso-level Operations:** Focuses on executing the strategies defined at the meso-level through WPs, coordinated by the General Assembly (GA) to bring the strategies to life. **Macro-level Oversight:** Entails a transnational steering approach, with external monitoring by the EQAB to ensure project activities align with overarching goals. This multi-tiered coordination will be formalized, monitored, and implemented through a Consortium Agreement (CA) that outlines the main management entities and their decision-making processes. This agreement, to be signed by all parties involved before the project commences, sets the foundation for structured governance. The project will be led by the General Project Coordinator (GPC), Dr Vassilios Kappatos, who will be responsible for the overall coordination of «WELDIFY», supported by a robust scientific team. As the Project Coordinator, Dr Vassilios Kappatos will act as the primary liaison with EACEA Officers and lead both the «SC» and «GA». Alongside the scientific team, he will oversee project monitoring, maintain communication within the Consortium, and manage financial and legal matters, ensuring the smooth running of all project meetings and the distribution of related documents. For administrative, legal, and financial tasks, Dr Vasileios Kappatos will rely on an in-house Management Support Team specialising in EU Project Management. This team, with a track record of successfully managing several EU-funded projects from start to finish, will guarantee high-quality management for WELDIFY. The scientific and technical management of

the project is structured around 7 Work Packages (WPs), each headed by a WP Leader (WPL) responsible for coordinating and overseeing the activities within their respective WP. This organisational structure ensures a comprehensive approach to managing the various aspects of the project.

Strategic Committee (SC)	General Assembly (GA)	WP Leaders (WPLs)	External Quality Advisory Board (EQAB)
<p>The (SC) of WELDIFY, comprising the GPC and the (WP) leaders, serves as the central decision-making body of the project. This committee is tasked with overseeing the execution of the project, including key aspects such as risk management, dispute resolution with effective task reallocation, and periodic reporting to ensure the project stays on track with its goals and timelines. Milestones and deliverables are utilised as primary metrics to gauge progress against the planned implementation</p>	<p>The GA plays a pivotal role in WELDIFY, tasked with deliberating on the project's technical direction and either confirming or amending the strategic guidelines established by the SC.</p> <p>Governed by the coordinator, the GA comprises representatives from each project partner, ensuring a broad and inclusive approach to decision making. Owing to its composition of high-level representatives, the GA also holds the authority to manage any consortium wide</p>	<p>WPLs oversee coordinating the operations of each WP (including activity management and implementation with the responsible activity leaders) in terms of meeting objectives reaching the milestones, and delivering appropriate outputs, according to the WP schedule. WPLs will manage</p>	<p>The EQAB members (scientists, industrial & policy representatives) are internationally renowned, independent experts working in the areas covered by WELDIFY.</p> <p>The EQAB will be managed by the SC and GPC. The EQAB will review technical results of the project and give non-binding advice towards further advancements to be achieved. They will join WELDIFY project meetings once per year.</p>

<p>schedule. Additionally, the SC is responsible for managing the IPR process, with the GPC leading the coordination efforts to ensure that all IPR-related matters are handled efficiently and effectively, protecting the interests and contributions of all project partners.</p>	<p>issues, providing a comprehensive oversight mechanism that integrates technical insight with overarching strategic objectives.</p>	<p>each activity and review the deliverables and report to the SC.</p>	
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Table 4 - WELDIFY Management / Organizational Structure

The decision-making mechanism of WELDIFY will be based such as: **Level 1: Strategic Committee (SC)** - Under the auspices of the General Project Coordinator (GPC) and contingent upon the concurrence of directly implicated partners, the SC adjudicates on the redistribution of tasks and/or resources across Work Packages (WPs), along with sanctioning protocols to facilitate efficacious routine operations. Such determinations may encompass significant modifications to the work plan or the reallocation of tasks and financial resources amongst consortium members, ensuring these adjustments do not materially alter the project's intended outcomes and deliverables. Additionally, the SC is vested with the authority to resolve intra-consortium disputes. Meetings of the SC are convened monthly via digital platforms and are aligned with the schedule of Project Meetings. **Level 2: General Assembly (GA)** - In instances where the SC is unable to formulate a consensus, the GA assumes the decision-making mantle. Decisions within the GA are derived through a majority vote, with each participating partner endowed with a singular vote, deployed when unanimity is unattainable. The GPC delineates the scope of decisions amenable to SC adjudication without GA intervention, particularly in matters of partner contention. **Level 3: Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA)** - Engagement of the EACEA is necessitated for decisions precipitating contractual modifications, such as the incorporation of new consortium beneficiaries or the substitution of existing ones. Following GA deliberation, the GPC communicates the requisite information to the EACEA, whose determinations are legally binding on the consortium. The EACEA's jurisdiction also extends to amendments necessitating GA ratification. Although urgent resolutions may necessitate electronic polling, preference is given to synchronous deliberations, be they virtual or physical, within the SC or GA forums.

4.2.13. Risks and risk-mitigation measures

Some preliminary risks and proposed risk-mitigation measures are included in the table below.

Risk No	Description	WP No	Proposed risk-mitigation measures
1	QUALITY	All WPs	The project will implement a rigorous quality control regime for all outputs, with quality assurance initially conducted via internal peer review, led by the quality manager. Following this, an external advisory board (EQAB) and an External Evaluator will conduct quality assessments at three stages for each output, covering the prototype/concept, interim draft, and final draft phases.
2	LACK OF COMMUNICATION	All WPs	The lead partner will set up and manage an email list that includes all essential contacts from each project partner, ensuring ongoing internal communication. Partners will provide informal updates during the monthly online meetings and submit formal reports biannually, focusing on project management and quality assessments.
3	IMPLEMENTATION DELAY	All WPs	Key risks include the potential failure to deliver all results before starting the virtual pilots, which could compromise their quality. To mitigate this risk, we will leverage the extensive experience of each project partner with Erasmus+ projects and the high calibre of staff involved in execution. Milestones and objectives will be closely monitored monthly, with corrective measures implemented promptly in the event of any delays.
4	FINANCIAL & ADMINISTRATIVE RISKS	WPI	Potential financial risks include underspending, overspending, payment delays, and reporting delays. To mitigate these, a budget spreadsheet will be developed to calculate and estimate expenditures. Costs will be reviewed and discussed during the initial steering group meeting. Regular comparisons between actual expenditures and deliverables will be conducted to ensure financial alignment and project progress.
5	NOT REACHING THE	WP5	All partners have secured involvement from cross-departmental staff profiles for the project. To ensure wide reach and engagement for dissemination and piloting

	PARTICIPANT TARGETS		events, we will extensively promote these events to large audiences. Additionally, we will involve local quadruple helix actors (academia, industry, government, and civil society) as supporters or co-organizers to gain multilateral endorsements and thus, enhance audience attraction. For events not meeting their targets, second trials will be conducted.
6	PLATFORM DEPLOYMENT	WP4, WP7	The project outputs align with the internal objectives of each partner, ensuring their seamless integration and utilisation across all organisational levels within the partnering institutions. An explicit exploitation plan will be developed in the initial months of the project, with formalisation occurring towards its conclusion.
7	LIMITED IMPACT OF DISSEMINATION	WP7	The project will focus on translating scientific knowledge into simple and engaging language to captivate the audience. We plan to organize project specific demonstrations and training events, encouraging the active involvement of relevant stakeholders, including participants from related projects, conferences, and other related activities. Additionally, professional marketing services will be utilised to enhance outreach and engagement.
8	PANDEMIC RISKS	WP5	WELDIFY is fully equipped to conduct all its activities online, with plans to further bolster internal digital competencies through the development of digital outputs. Given that most of the partners are knowledge-based institutions, their operations are largely unaffected by pandemic-related restrictions, ensuring uninterrupted progress and collaboration.
9	DATA SHARING RELUCTANCE	WP5	The participating companies will establish non-disclosure agreements with the participants by formulating formal internship contracts for the trainees.
10	COMPETITIVE COURSES	WP2	We will diligently keep track of the latest advancements in the field and adjust our work accordingly by redirecting our research efforts and incorporating findings from external sources.

Table 5 – WELDIFY Critical Risks and Risk management strategy

4.2.14. Project Management Arrangements

The coordination team (CERTH) will oversee the distribution of resources among partners, guided by a comprehensive Consortium Agreement. This document will cover crucial aspects of the partnership, such as legal responsibilities, rights, conflict of interest, confidentiality, open-access licensing, intellectual property rights, decision-making frameworks, and quality control measures. It will detail each partner's tasks, the timing of these activities, and the associated budgets, ensuring clarity on roles, responsibilities, and financial allocations. Examples of such matters are legal obligations, rights and responsibilities, conflict of interests, confidentiality issues, the use of open-access licenses, IPR issues, decision-making procedures, voting processes, project oversight and Quality Control, conflict resolution processes, description of tasks (detailed spreadsheet as per allocated role and responsibilities to include name of each WP and activity to take part in, specific task, expected input and output, comments on format/specificity), timing of activities (detailed spreadsheet with the specific timeframe for delivering each task, indicative start and end date), estimated budget (general overview of project budget, detailed overview of allocated budget as per agreed roles, responsibilities and program rules, tasks to be carried out, cost to be covered, number of units allocated, budget per unit allocated), project Implementation plan (to include all rules /financial and management/ and requirements to be followed during the project lifetime) and the rest of the legal provisions related to suspension and termination, financial provisions, payment arrangements, recovery, reimbursement, etc. will be outlined. Other important matters will be included in the Consortium Agreement, such as payment and reporting procedures, scope, timeframe, bank accounts, data controller and communication details of partners, applicable law, special provisions, etc. Upon notification from EACEA about the project's funding, the coordinator will finalise the Consortium Agreement and will be signed by all partners at a very early stage of the project, ensuring that each partner is perfectly knowledgeable on what, when and how they will be contributing to project deployment. To support better implementation, pairing among partners (administrative mentorship) will be done to help less experienced consortium members handle the implementation flow & administration flow of the project: CERTH-CTA; EWF-HELIX; IIW-ISIM; HU-IMPACTCI-SUDOTIM; REDASP- CSC.

Deliverables and **output schedules** will be drawn up by the organisation responsible for leading each output, agreed with the project manager (PM) clearly stating the expectations and contributions of consortium members to each output. This will be incorporated into the project agenda. The PM will ensure that regular communication takes place between all partners using emails, teleconferencing, and cloud computing applications to facilitate discussions and share project documents, ensuring smooth and effective partnership working and exploiting opportunities for cross-institutional collaborations and dissemination activities.

Meetings will primarily be held virtually to overcome any logistical challenges and optimise project focus, with provisions for in-person meetings if feasible (and always combined with key training events). Budget will be allocated just in case the opportunity arises for several face-to-face meetings (less than 50% of the total meetings). The formal semestrial meetings will take place at key stages such as: Meeting 1 – kick-off (M1, in person in Thessaloniki Greece organised by CERTH). Meeting 2 (M6, in person in Nicosia, Cyprus organised by CSC). Meeting 3 (M12, online, organised by ISIM with the support of HELIX - online train the trainers). Meeting 4 (M18, in person, organised in Portugal – Lisbon by EWF and IMPACTSCI in conjunction with presentations from the WBL pilot organised by EWF). Meeting 5 (M24, in person in Greece by YET in conjunction with presentations from the WBL pilot organised by YET). Meeting 6 (M30, online, by REDASP with online presentations from the WBL pilot organised by REDASP). Meeting 7 (M36, closure and final launching event in Spain by CTA in conjunction with presentations from the WBL pilot organised by CTA).

A dedicated **strategy for monitoring project milestones** and addressing any challenges includes the production of interim progress reports and annual summaries of the project's achievements. Regular virtual meetings will support continuous engagement and oversight across the project lifecycle. To achieve this, three interim progress reports will be produced describing the project's progress towards achieving the set goals, as well as two annual project reports, complemented by monthly Teams/Zoom/Webex meetings. Partners will lead on outputs to which best reflect their expertise. The PM & SG will agree with all partners the protocols and financial and monitoring procedures, communication means, delivery strategy, timeframes and will develop and agree the detailed project work plan. The project coordinator oversees the financial management of the project, but all partners will help to develop and agree on the financial procedures and distribution of resources required for each activity. The lead partner/coordinator will also ensure the following: Contractual, legal, ethical, financial, and administrative management of the consortium. This structured approach ensures a transparent, collaborative, and efficient process towards fulfilling the project's objectives, with a strong focus on accountability, inclusivity, and effective communication across all stages of the project.

Data Management Plan for primary data (Surveys, participant data, etc., in compliance with GDPR¹); Ensuring the Consortium Agreement (CA) is kept updated and managed appropriately; Organising and chairing Project Management and transnational meetings; Collation of cost statements, coordination of payments and distribution to relevant consortium members; Facilitating audits and overall communication and interaction with EACEA; Coordinate project

¹ Guidelines | European Data Protection Supervisor

activities among activity leaders. Ultimately, task management-wise, WELDIFY will adopt the following structure: Each Work Package (WP) is implemented by a core group of partners, led by the respective WP leader. Each Task within every WP is also led by the Task owner. These are the basic coordination characteristics for managing the project's implementation ensuring that every activity is in-line with the initial proposal, the grant agreement with EACEA and the Consortium Agreement. In MI, each partner will nominate one representative member to take important operational decisions on behalf of its organisation. Additionally, all consortium members will have to provide nominations for core groups (WP and Task managers), as per allocated roles within each work package.

4.2.15. Transnational dimension & EU impact/interest & cross-border cooperation potential

Transnational cooperation is required and beneficial because: The skills gap observed in participating countries is similar, indicating a shared need that transnational EU collaboration can address. Moreover, in the involved countries, over 53% of digital learners in higher education and VET in these countries experience challenges with inclusion and engagement. Countries in Southern (Italy, Greece, Cyprus) and Eastern Europe (Romania, Serbia, Portugal) report the highest rates of unqualified trainers, indicating a significant need for improved training quality systems. Transnational efforts can help overcome this issue. Similarly, the disparity between Eastern and Western/Central Europe (e.g. Belgium, Sweden, Austria) in terms of upskilling, inclusion, and access to quality educational resources can be reduced through such cooperative initiatives. By working at a transnational level, which allows for the blending of specific cultural backgrounds, behaviors, and nuances, leading to more uniform and applicable outcomes that can be extended to countries outside this cooperation circle involved in WELDIFY. In addition, the WELDIFY project aims to foster EU-wide cooperation and harmonise qualifications through digital content and a transnational approach. It focuses on training in CMW to address challenges in transnational industries and ensure operational coordination across the EU. The initiative also aims to establish a WELDIFY alumni network for international collaboration and a virtual factory platform to facilitate real-life knowledge application, drawing contributions from industrial and educational providers EU-wide.

4.3. Gantt chart

The schedule listing the project's milestones, activities, and tasks with estimations in terms of duration is shown in the Gantt chart below.

Table 6 – Gantt Chart

ACTIVITY	YEAR 1				YEAR 2				YEAR 3			
	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4	Q 1	Q 2	Q 3	Q 4
WPI: Task 1.1 Consortium management – Establish a Project Coordination Team												
WPI: Task 1.2 EACEA Reporting												
WPI: Task 1.3 IPR, legal & ethical obligations management												
WPI: Task 1.4 External quality assurance board (EQAB)												
WP2: Task 2.1 EIT-compliant overarching learning outcomes.												
WP2: Task 2.2 EIT-compliant CMW toolkit for trainers												
WP2: Task 2.3 EIT-compliant CMW toolkit for learners.												
WP2: Task 2.4 Accreditation & integration with quality and credit recognition frameworks												
WP2: Task 2.5 Revise and finalize the training modules based on feedback from the pilot testing												
WP3: Task 3.1 Design a micro-credential framework for CMW learners												

WP3: Task 3.2 Develop assessment and certification criteria for CMW training.												
WP3: Task 3.3 - Certificate development & automated assessment/verification tool												
WP4: Task 4.1 WELDIFY CMW platform												
WP4: Task 4.2 Security, data protection, and GDPR												
WP4: Task 4.3 WELDIFY CMW online platform beta version												
WP4: Task 4.4 WELDIFY CMW platform sign off												
WP5: Task 5.1 Design and plan work-based learning (WBL) pilots in collaboration with industry partners across EU countries.												
WP5: Task 5.2 Digital train the trainers												

WP5: Task 5.3 WBL Pilot 1: Greece												
WP5: Task 5.4 - WBL Pilot 2: Romania												
WP5: Task 5.5 - WBL Pilot 3: Greece												
WP5 Task 5.6 - WBL Pilot 4: Serbia												
WP5: Task 5.7 - WBL Pilot 5: Spain												
WP5: Task 5.8 - WBL Pilot 6: Sweden												

The PC monitors and coordinates the work plan. After **18 months**, the WELDIFY project will provide the reporting on activities and resources, and any deviations from the original work plan will be explained and justified in the periodic reports. The Project Coordinator will revise the Gantt chart accordingly, updating it with actual effort reported, actual month of submission of the deliverables and main project meetings that took place. In particular, the Project Officer will monitor the effort allocation to the tasks/deliverables provided by partners in order to check the status of the use of resources.

The WP leader is responsible for the schedule within his/her WP and he/she must communicate with the PC in case of any problems or delays that may arise during the project timeline.

4.4. Deliverable Process

The list of WELDIFY deliverables is reported in the following table.

Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month number)	Description (including format and language)
D1.1	Project management plan	WPI	CERTH	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M3	A report (50 pages, English) containing all internal management and coordination procedures.
D1.2	Data management plan	WPI	CERTH	[DMP – Data Manage]	[PU – Public]	M3	A document (10 pages, English) explaining the WELDIFYs' data

				ment Plan]			management strategy.
D2.1	CMW toolkit for trainers and learners	WP2	EFW	[R – Documen t, report]	[PU – Public]	M12	Developed modules for trainers and learners, 5 modules for each (10 in total): 600 slides with voice/video overlay, 10 storyboards, 2 booklet (300 pages), collection of 20 demonstrative videos, 2 interactive learner- persona based simulator as assessment tool (360 multiple choice questions) and 2 WebQuest per module related to work-based learning practices. All formally approved by the EQAB. Languages & translations: EN,

							RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT, DE.
D2.2	ECTS & ECVET Certification Documents	WP2	HELIX	<i>[R – Document, report]</i> <i>[OTHER]</i>	<i>[PU – Public]</i>	M12	A collection of ECTS & ECVET accreditation processes issued by each relevant partner as mentioned in Task 2.4.
D3.1	Micro Credential Framework Document	WP3	HELIX	<i>[R – Document, report]</i>	<i>[PU – Public]</i>	M13	Outline of the certification criteria and process. Size: 50 Pages report available in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT, DE.
D3.2	Assessment and Certification Tools	WP3	YET	<i>DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc</i>	<i>[PU – Public]</i>	M16	Automated Europass digital credential system embedded with the WP4 platform.
D4.1	WELDIFY Platform	WP4	YET	<i>DEC – Websites, patent filings, videos, etc</i>	<i>[PU – Public]</i>	M22	Platform released publicly (web service) with fully functioning & tested modules. Available in in multiple languages: EN,

							RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT, DE.
D5.1	WBL Pilots	WP5	CTA	DEM – Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	[PU – Public]	M28	Pilots implemented in Greece (2), Romania, Serbia, Spain, Sweden with learners engaged and certified.
D5.2	Evaluation & Improvement Report	WP5	HELIX	R – Document, report	[PU – Public]	M34	Progress and final evaluation report with recommendations for improving WP2, WP4 based on the WBL Pilots and Mass Pilot. A document of 25 pages issued in English.
D6.1	Quality assurance plan and report	WP6	HELIX	R – Document, report	[PU – Public]	M3, M18, M36	An integrated report (90 pages) containing the quality assurance plan & key performance indicators (will be issued in EN) and the results of the two

							periodic quality reviews
D6.2	External evaluation strategy and report	WP6	CERTH	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M6, M18, M36	Report (at least 100 pages in English) explaining the external evaluation strategy and the results (interim and final) of the strategy's deployment
D7.1	Communication and dissemination plan	WP7	EITM	R – Document, report	[PU – Public]	M3	A report (50 pages, English).
D7.2	Communication and dissemination material, tools and events	WP7	EITM	R – Document, report	[PU – Public]	M36	Report (50 pages, English) presenting all communication and dissemination material developed and events organized and participated. These will include: (a) project website (content will be made available in n EN, RO, GR, IT,

						<p>SE, SRB, ES, PT, DE), logos, document templates & social media accounts; (b) partner-level (decentralized) mailing list with selected target groups (GDPR compliant) of at least 25 000 contacts; (c) 6 newsletters (digital) with limited printed version (600) distributed to at least 25 000 contacts in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT; (d) 6 videos developed and disseminated to 25 000 contacts (videos will be in English with subtitles in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT); (e) 3 policy briefings (15 pages each) will be developed and</p>
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							made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT; (f) 8 open day dissemination events that will be hosted by (each) partner; (g) At least 6 appearances in TV/radio/conventional media will be produced.
D7.3	Impact measurement matrix with a preliminary impact assessment	WP7	EFW	R – Document, report	[PU – Public]	M3, M36	Impact assessment report (40 pages in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT
D7.4	WEDIFY sustainability, exploitation commercialization plan	WP7	HELIX	[R – Document, report]	[PU – Public]	M36	One report (20 pages) will be developed and made available in EN, RO, GR, IT, SE, SRB, ES, PT

Table 7 – List of Deliverables

4.4.1. The Short-Deliverable Policy

The right size for a given deliverable depends largely on the topic, the purpose, etc., but very long deliverables create several problems:

- It takes longer to write and revise them;
- They are not easily readable and prone to lose their focus.

Therefore, the deliverables should be clear about the objective, and then be very concise about the content to include in the documents. The focus must be clear and specific. It must also avoid

repeating content from other documents (always use references for that). It is of utmost importance to have a clear Executive Summary, an Introduction containing the objectives and the structure of the document, as well as a Conclusions section. All official project documents will be produced following the templates and guidelines developed by the consortium, in accordance with the European Commission's (EC) standards.

The official editing tool for deliverables will be: Microsoft Word 2016 or newer. Other editing suite tools can be used under the following conditions:

- Deliverable editor must agree with contributors in advance.
- Deliverable editor must provide the template for the new format that must match with the official template provided by the EC.
- If a contributor does not use the selected editing tool/format, the deliverable editor is responsible for integrating these contributions in the official editing format/tool.

4.5. «EC» Participant Portal

It is the official EC Portal for the submission of deliverables, technical and financial reporting, ethical requirements and amendments, specifically:

- Submission of project deliverables;
- Periodic Technical & Financial Reporting;
- Final Technical & Financial Reporting;
- Risk & Issues Management;
- Requests for Amendments;
- Implementation of Ethics Requirements;
- Submission of Final Project Results Report.

4.6. Project Meetings

Interactive management meetings and technical meetings play an important role in the project. WELDIFY meetings include the following.

Event No	Participant	Description					Attendees
		Name	Type	Area	Location	Duration (days)	Total
E1.1	All	Transnational meeting 1	Project meeting	Project coordination	Thessaloniki, Greece	1.5	26
E1.2	All	Transnational meeting 2	Project meeting	Project coordination	Nicosia, Cyprus	1.5	26
E1.3	All	Transnational meeting 3	Project meeting	Project coordination	Online	1.5	26
E1.4	All	Transnational meeting 4	Project meeting	Project coordination	Lisbon, Portugal	1.5	26
E1.5	All	Transnational meeting 5	Project meeting	Project coordination	Thessaloniki, Greece	1.5	26
E1.6	All	Transnational meeting 6	Project meeting	Project coordination	Online	1.5	26
E1.7	All	Transnational meeting 7	Project Meeting	Project coordination	Spain	1.5	26
E5.2	Digital train the trainers	Trainers pre-pilot	Mobility/ Training	Train the Trainers	Online	5	24
E5.3	CERTH	WBL Pilot 1	Internship /event	Automotive -	Greece	90	20

				preventive welding strategies			
E5.4	ISIM	WBL Pilot 2	Internship /event	Automotive - assembly line welding	Romania	90	20
E5.5	YET	WBL Pilot 3	Internship /event	Construction - metallic infrastructure joining	Greece	90	10
E5.6	REDASP	WBL Pilot 4	Internship /event	Automotive - frame joining	Serbia	90	20
E5.7	CTA	WBL Pilot 5	Internship /event	Construction/ infrastructure joining	Spain	90	20
E5.8	HU	WBL Pilot 6	Internship / event	IT/IOT	Sweden	90	20
E7.1	CERTH	Open day 1	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Greece	1	50
E7.2	EITM	Open day 2	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Austria	1	50
E7.3	EFW	Open day 3	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Portugal	1	50
E7.4	HU	Open day 4	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Sweden	1	50
E7.5	CTA	Open day 5	Dissemination event	Project output promotion	Spain	1	50

E7.6	REDASP	Open day 6	Dissemina tion event	Project output promotion	Serbia	1	50
E7.7	ISIM	Open day 7	Dissemina tion event	Project output promotion	Romania	1	50
E7.8	CSC	Open day 8	Dissemina tion event	Project output promotion	Cyprus	1	50

Table 8 - Project Meetings

4.6.1. Organisation of the meetings

In the paragraphs below, best practices for the organisation of the WELDIFY meetings are described.

Types of meetings

During the project, **three types** of meetings will be conducted:

- i) Physical meetings
- ii) Video conferences
- iii) Conference calls

The consortium has planned to meet in person at least once a year, with periodic progress meetings held over a period of 1.5 to 2 days at the premises of project partners. To ensure equal opportunities for all partners, hosts for the in-person meetings have been selected randomly, without any additional requirements. Whenever possible, project meetings may be organized in conjunction with major events that WELDIFY partners are planning or interested in attending.

The consortium partners are located in different countries. For the physical meetings, it is important to consider:

- If another physical meeting is scheduled at the same time, project partners should explore the possibility of conducting both meetings jointly to optimize costs.
- Proper evaluation of timing, avoiding critical periods such as holidays and major international events whenever possible.
- Assessment of the selected location and city, considering ease of access and travel convenience.

- Consideration of previous meeting locations to ensure equal opportunities for all partners to host meetings.

Conference call meetings are planned to facilitate partner collaboration and the organization of additional meetings. These meetings follow the same rules as standard meetings and will be used for progress updates and work package (WP) meetings whenever necessary. The meetings, whether physical or virtual, will be scheduled by mutual agreement of the consortium partners through electronic polls.

Responsibilities of partners

The hosting partner should provide information regarding arrival and departure times and, where applicable, hotel recommendations. They are also responsible for organizing coffee breaks, lunches, and dinners, taking into account any special dietary requirements. Additionally, a conference call bridge (Meeting links) should be set up to facilitate the participation of those unable to attend in person, such as WELDIFY members (researchers, industry stakeholders, external advisors) or EC representatives.

Agendas and minutes will be prepared and shared by the chairperson of the meeting and shall be made available to all Consortium members on the «Google Drive» repository (Shared folder) of the WELDIFY project.

Each Partner:

- Should be present or represented at any meeting;
- May appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting; and
- Shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

Each participant to a meeting should contribute to the meeting preparation by providing in advance to the meeting:

- Contributions to the agenda;
- Preparation of presentations;
- Working documents: normally the main subjects discussed during a meeting will be documented by discussion papers or presentations. As far as possible, these means should be distributed in advance and not during the meeting itself, since otherwise the participants will be unable to be prepared for the meeting;
- Feedback on the minutes in case of disagreement;

- Execution of actions and respect of decisions.

The PC will have the special responsibility of contributing to the definition of meeting objectives, and the preparation of decisions, agenda and minutes. The PC for plenary meetings or the WP leader for the WP meetings will be the chairperson, unless decided otherwise.

Agenda of the meetings

Each meeting must have an agenda. The draft agenda should be distributed **in advance (14 days)**, to inform participants about the topics to be discussed and to give them the opportunity to suggest changes to the agenda which must then be re-circulated. Comments and integration can be done before sharing the final agenda **(5 days before the meeting)**. The agenda lists the subjects which are planned to be discussed. It is an instrument to assist the facilitator in monitoring the meeting. Secretarial work is also minimised by a well-structured agenda.

Each agenda contains some **standard subjects** with the following structure:

- Type of meeting
- List of participants
- «Place»
- «Date»
- «Time» Opening and welcome.
- «Time» Objectives of the meeting and agreement about the agenda.
- «Time» Remarks on previous minutes (only if applicable).
- «Time» Action points (only if applicable).
- «Time» Meeting specific subjects.
- Explanation of subject (issues to decide upon, actions to decide, etc.)
- «Time» Sum up and closing:
 - I. Date and place of next meeting(s) (only if applicable)
 - II. Define list of open issues.
 - III. Summarise decisions and actions list.

«Place» is the location of the meeting, «Date» is the day for which the agenda is valid; multiple-day meetings have an agenda for each day. «Time» defines the planned time to start discussion on a topic. If breaks, lunch and dinner are planned, these events should be included in the agenda. During a meeting the agenda can be modified by adding items if it's necessary.

Minutes

Particular attention must be given to the follow-ups of the meeting, it is recommended to send the minutes quickly, check commitment on decisions and actions with absent partners, and ensure that decisions are respected and actions executed.

The PC for general meetings or the WP leader in charge of the agenda is responsible for the minutes drafting. S/he can appoint a person to produce written minutes, which shall be the formal record of what was discussed during the meeting. The minutes shall be sent to all project members (preferably within **10 calendar days of the meeting**). The minutes shall be considered as accepted if no one sends an objection (within **7 calendar days from receiving them**).

The minutes will therefore constitute a sort of «**pocket handbook**» with all the data that each of the participants will always have to keep an eye on.

The minutes will reflect major issues that have been discussed. All minutes of periodic meetings will have the same structure. Minutes should contain the following information:

- Meeting date;
- Location;
- Author;
- Participants;
- Objective of the meeting (brief);
- Actual agenda;
- List of documents distributed during the meeting with reference to the author (if applicable);

and for each point addressed as part of the agenda:

- summary of discussion (if relevant);
- decision;
- open issues;

- action;
- supporting information (if relevant).
- summary of the action list;
- place and date of the next meeting (if applicable).

Minutes of meetings involving the EC shall also be distributed via email for review by the EC officer. Action updates should be regularly (monthly) be sent to the EC. For all meetings involving the EC, the EC shall be asked to review the minutes before their approval.

5. Management Plan

5.1. Review Process

Quality plan is an integral part of Project Management. As a prerequisite to its preparation, the Quality Control Panel (in its initial version, consisted of representatives from the consortium, PC, and QAM) has reviewed all requirements in order to determine the necessary activities that need to be planned.

It has been prepared early in the project in order to demonstrate and provide the Consortium with the assurance that:

- the contract requirements and conditions have been reviewed,
- effective quality control has taken place, and
- the quality system is appropriate.

To ensure the relevance of the quality plan, the Quality Control Panel (including four EQAB members and an external evaluator) should conduct quality reviews, throughout the duration of the contract, and when contractual changes occur. The Quality Control Panel shall ensure that the quality plan is available to all partners concerned and that its requirements are met.

In order to ensure a clear structure of the quality assurance procedure, the following steps have to be taken into account:

1. **A first check** of the consistency in style and content is to be done internally in each Work Package Deliverable. This task is carried out by the **Work Package leader**.
2. **Three (3) weeks** before the due date of the deliverable, the task leader for the deliverable informs the reviewers nominated about the status of the deliverable.
3. **At least 10 days** before the due date, the deliverable is sent by the task leader to the nominated reviewer(s) for quality control.

4. The reviewers have **1 week** to read and comment on the deliverable.
5. The deliverable **authors revise their reports according** to the comments received by the reviewers.
6. **Three days** before the due date, the deliverable authors send the updated deliverable to the project Coordinator. The PC performs a final consistency check to ensure proper formatting and consistency with other project deliverables.
7. The project Coordinator forwards the deliverable to the Project Officer and publishes the deliverable on the Project Platform.

5.2. Evaluation

The evaluation of the deliverables should be based on the following criteria:

1. General comments, which include:
 - Deliverable contents thoroughness
 - Correspondence to project and programme objectives
2. Specific comments, which include:
 - Relevance
 - Response to user needs
 - Soundness of the methodological framework
 - Quality of achievements
 - Quality of presentation of achievements
 - Check the layout, format, spelling, etc.

The evaluation and rating will give a statement whether the deliverable is accepted or not or if modifications are necessary. The quality of the deliverable will be rated as follows:

- Accepted as it is
- Revise with proposed modifications/comments to be addressed
- Rejected based on substantiated comments.

6. Documentation Control

6.1. Document coding

There will be a unique project document coding system to ensure proper tracking, version control, and organization of project-related documents, as indicated in the table below.

Table 9 –

Document Code	Document Type
D	Deliverable
WP	Work Package
PR	Work Packages Plans and Progress Reports
M	Minutes, Action Lists, Decision Lists
C	Correspondence between Partners
L	Legal documents
COM	Commercial documents
GI	Documents of general interest
PU	Public documents
OTH	Other subjects

Table 9 - Project document coding system

All official consortium documents in the above table, **except for the Deliverables**, are collectively referred to hereafter as **Project Internal Reports (IR)**.

6.2. Document referencing and Templates

There is a unique document referencing scheme. This is not applicable however for informal data and views exchange between partners. It is only valid for official consortium documents, falling in one of the aforementioned categories. The project's internal documents template and

referencing scheme is being included in Annex B. For official deliverables, a different template and referencing scheme will be used, as presented in Annex A.

6.2.1. Documents standards and layouts

The naming convention for deliverables is the following:

«Dx.y_shortname_V00.00.00.status»

Explanation:

«Dx.y» is the deliverable number, as reported in the cover page of the document, where **x** is the **work package number**; and **y** is a number for **each deliverable**. The resulting identifier must be one of those listed in List of Deliverables of the **DoA (Description of Action)**.

«**Short name**» is a brief name, decided by the document's author(s), that can be easily related to the document content (it can be the title of the deliverable as in the DoA).

«vn.mm.pp» is the document version.

- Working drafts = last two digits: 00-99 = 00.00.xx.
- (First) draft for submission/review: 00.01.00
- Subsequent working drafts to use last digits couple again, e.g. 00.01.01
- Accepted (first) version (EC): 01.00.00
- The version number has to be also visible on the front page and in the headline of each page.

«**Status**» is the status of the document, that can be a) working b) draft or c) final.

Official project deliverables should have a first page template as presented in Annex A. They should also use the structure and page layout (headers / footers) suggested in this Annex. Furthermore, the mainly technical deliverables should abide by the following rules:

- Have a list of abbreviations used within the deliverable.
- Have a Table of Contents.
- Have a List of Figures.
- Have a List of Tables.
- Start with a one-page Executive Summary.
- Include a References (or Bibliography) section after the Conclusions section.

Include all detailed technical and other information in Annexes. In addition, the authors of a document and the internal approval process will be included in each document.

The EU emblem has to be displayed in all documents and the following disclaimers have to be included:

Funding: «*This Deliverable is part of a project that has received funding from the European Commission under grant agreement No 101184218 under Erasmus+ Programme (ERASMUS)*».

6.3. Data Communication Protocols

All documents and computer data files sent either by Internet or e-mail are to be VIRUS checked before issue and to be screened on receipt. If a VIRUS is found, then action is to be taken to purge both the system infected and to notify the sender to prevent a re-occurrence. If acknowledgement is requested, an explicit request will be included by the sender at the end of the message (email, fax, etc.), stating "Please Acknowledge". Then, the recipient is required to send a message of acknowledgement within the **next two (2) working days**.

6.4. Participation in events and publications

In addition to official project events, the following are considered dissemination activities:

- Publications in relevant magazines
- Presentations in Conferences
- Participation in relevant projects meetings
- Participation in non-project workshops, forums, and events

Any project participant planning to engage in such activities must inform and obtain formal approval from both the Steering Committee and the Project Coordinator (CERTH/HIT).

For any conference presentation or journal publication, the following procedure will be followed:

- Oral agreement of all participants being present at the meeting, or written agreement of the PC. In the latter case, it is the PC's responsibility to request approval from all interested / involved participants. The written answer should be sent from the requesting participant within **5 working days** from receipt from the PC. Otherwise, it is supposed to be positive.
- The draft paper is then circulated to all project participants, at least **15 days** before submission. All participants may object to the publication of confidential data or to non-inclusion of their name, if their work is also included, within 5 days from receipt of the

draft paper. Comments are to be sent to the publishing partner with copies to the PC. Then the CERTH/HIT should restructure the draft paper accordingly.

- After paper acceptance, a copy of the final paper will be sent to the PC who will forward the paper abstract and publication information to the Project Officer.

In case of too short deadlines, the actions prior to abstract or paper submission might be realized quicker, after consultation with the Coordinator.

The above rules will be strictly applied and checked by the PC in order to:

- avoid repetition of publication of the same work;
- avoid publication of restrictive and/or commercial in confidence data;
- avoid misunderstandings between participants and publication of one's work without proper referencing;
- secure optimum use of dissemination resources of the project;
- guarantee proper archiving of all dissemination material.

7. Internal Communication Strategies

The main documents that will be circulated between partners are the following:

- **Quarterly reports**
- **Technical Deliverables**
- **Internal Reports**

Regarding electronic communication, a series of mailing lists will be compiled to enhance the communication between WELDIFY partners. The mailing lists that will be developed are the following:

- One mailing list for all WELDIFY Partners, which will contain two (or more) e-mail addresses per partner. This mailing list should be used, in case an email is addressed to the whole network.
- One mailing list for Work Package leaders. This mailing list contains from one to four contacts from each partner.

To ensure fine-tuned communication among the partners, the following email visibility rules will be observed: all emails must include the project name in the subject line and a header description. Additionally, the Project Coordinator (PC) will be included in all project-related emails.

The mailing lists will be distributed as text files to all WELDIFY Partners and will also be uploaded in Google Drive (WELDIFY shared folder), an Internal partners' area that constitutes a documents repository and project management tool. Through Google Drive, the participants will be able to exchange documents, download the presentations and minutes of the meetings and in general communicate with one another.

8. Project Reporting and Monitoring

The action is divided into the following Reporting Periods²

- RPI: from month 1 to month 18
- RP2: from month 19 to month 36

The Project Coordinator must submit a periodic report within **60 days following the end of each reporting period. Each WP leader should submit a WP Report to the Project Coordinator**, who assembles the parts and elaborates the Progress Report. In addition, the Coordinator must submit to the EC the technical and financial reports, including when needed the requests for payment and must be drawn up using forms and templates provided by the EC.

8.1. Periodic Technical/Financial Reporting

A Periodic Technical and Financial Progress Report shall be submitted via the **«EC» Participant Portal** every six months within **60 working days** following the end of the Reporting Period. The content of the Technical and Financial Progress Reports is detailed in the Portal User Manual. An extract is provided below; however, the latest version of the Portal User Manual remains the reference.

8.1.1. Periodic Technical Report

A Technical Progress Report shall provide a qualitative summary of the work performed according to

the **EC Participant Portal guidelines**. It consists of **Part A** and **Part B**:

Part A contains:

1. the cover page;
2. a publishable summary, including:

²WELDIFY Grant Agreement

- An executive statement on the progress made and key issues;
 - Achievements made in the last reporting period, i.e. milestones, meetings, and tasks key data;
 - Main targets and events over the next reporting period.
3. Tables covering issues related to the project implementation (e.g., Work Packages, Deliverables, Milestones, etc.) which includes:
- Deliverables (indicating the % completion of deliverables);
 - Milestones;
 - Ethical Issues (if applicable);
 - Critical implementation risks and mitigation measures;
 - Dissemination & exploitation of results;
 - Impact on SMEs (if applicable);
 - Open Research Data (if applicable);
 - Gender.

4. The answers to the questionnaire covering issues related to the project implementation and the economic and social impact, notably in the context of the «Erasmus+» programme key performance indicators and the «Erasmus+» programme monitoring requirements.

Part A is generated via the Participant Portal based on the information entered by the participants through the periodic report and continuous reporting modules. The participants can update the information in the continuous reporting module at any time during the project lifetime.

Part B of the periodic technical report provides the narrative part that includes explanations of the work carried out by the beneficiaries during the reporting period. It will include:

1. Explanations of the work carried out by all beneficiaries and linked third parties during the reporting period;
2. An overview of the progress towards the project objectives, justifying the differences between work expected under Annex I and work actually performed, if any;
3. An update on Risks and Issues.

Part B needs to be uploaded as a PDF document. It must be consistent with the template of Part B Periodic Technical report.

8.1.2. Financial Report

1. The Periodic report for Additional pre-financing on M18 consists of a statement on the use of the previous pre-financing and a payment request. To release the next pre-financing in full, 70% of previous pre-financing has to be consumed.
2. The periodic report for the final payment on M36 is based on the delivery and completion of the work packages and deliverables at the final report stage. The evaluation of WPs takes place upon the submission of the final report.

8.1.3. Final Periodic Technical/Financial Report

The Final Report covers the whole project and is composed of a Final Technical and a Final Financial part. It is delivered within **60 days** from the completion of the Action. In case not all deliverables have been submitted in time before the completion of the Action, the Project may ask for an extension, as an exception, using the Amendment procedure.

8.1.4. Final Periodic Technical Report

The Final Periodic Technical Report is a publishable summary of the entire project. It provides:

1. An overview of the project scope and objectives;
2. The achieved results and main conclusions achieved at the end of the project based on the criteria defined by EC supporting the claimed project readiness to transfer its results to the next R&I phase;
3. The performed communication and dissemination actions;
4. The Exploitation and follow-up activities proposed for the next stage of the R&I lifecycle;
5. The socio-economic impact of the project;
6. An up-to-date link to the project website;
7. Project logos, diagrams, photographs and videos illustrating its work (if available).

The final summary must be written in a style understandable for a non-specialist audience. The Coordinator must ensure that none of the material submitted for publication includes confidential or 'EU classified' information.

8.1.5. Final Periodic Financial Report

The Final Periodic Financial Report includes:

1. The final summary financial statement that is automatically created by the system (consolidating the data from all individual financial statements for all beneficiaries and linked third parties, for all reporting periods) and that constitutes the request for payment of the balance;
2. In some cases (and for some beneficiaries/linked third parties) it must be accompanied by a certificate on the financial statements – CFS (one certificate per beneficiary/linked third party).

9. Risks and Preventive Actions

9.1. Risk and conflict management

Every effort will be made to identify potential risks and conflicts as early as possible. The impact of such risks and conflicts on project objectives will be assessed by the project manager and the work package leaders. The impacts will be actively addressed through an early assessment and elimination of risk through the detection of proper actions and management of any dysfunctional conflicts. In cases of dysfunctional conflict, the Consortium will follow a mediation approach to identify possible alternatives and mutually select the one that is in the interest of the project objectives.

9.2. Corrective and preventive actions

Apart from the particular procedures adopted to assess the quality of the Project Deliverables, this section deals with issues related to the general performance of the Partners and the quality of their work-related outcome.

- The Coordinator is responsible for implementing and recording changes in procedures, resulting from corrective actions. Established procedures established are to ensure:
- Effective handling of all complaints,
- Reports of non-conformities,
- Investigation of the cause of non-conformities in relation to the quality system,
- Recording the results of the investigation,
- Determining the corrective / preventive action needed to eliminate the cause of the non-conformity,
- Application of controls to ensure that corrective action is taken and is effective,
- Initiation of preventative action and application of controls to ensure that it is effective,

- Ensuring that relevant information on actions taken is submitted for review.

The Coordinator is responsible for resolving matters of complaint under this procedure, in agreement with the Steering Committee. All complaints have to be investigated and corrective action agreed. The QAM informs all involved for the complaints and the actions being taken. The complaints are recorded in a Complaint Register and are being controlled. Corrective actions are recorded and all involved are informed of the action taken.

10. References

1. Guidelines | European Data Protection Supervisor
2. WELDIFY Grant Agreement

11. Annexes

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Deep-tech driven inclusive and socially-aware circular material joining & welding for a safe future

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